

Learning Push-Grasping in Dense Clutter

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Abstract—Robotic grasping in highly cluttered environments remains a challenging task due to the lack of collision free grasp affordances. In such conditions, non-prehensile actions could help to increase such affordances. We propose a multi-fingered push-grasping policy that creates enough space for the fingers to wrap around an object to perform a stable power grasp, using a single primitive action. Our approach learns a direct mapping from visual observations to actions and is trained in a fully end-to-end manner. To achieve a more efficient learning, we decouple the action space by learning separately the robot hand pose and finger configuration. Experiments in simulation demonstrate that the proposed push-grasping policy achieves higher grasp success rate over baselines and it can generalize to unseen objects. Furthermore, although training is performed in simulation, the learned policy is robustly transferred to a real environment without a significant drop in success rate. Qualitative results, code, pre-trained models and simulation environments are available at <https://robot-clutter.github.io/ppg>.

I. INTRODUCTION

REALISTIC environments that robots should operate are highly cluttered and uncertain, prohibiting the robot’s fingers from reaching and grasping an object properly. Uncertainty exists either due to occlusions that clutter creates or due to unknown dynamic object properties, such as friction, preventing the robotic system from planning robust grasps due to incomplete information. Although research has focused on precision grasping for dealing with clutter scenes, it cannot provide the increased stability of power grasping, especially under uncertainty of the dynamic object properties. Hence, finding pre-grasp manipulation policies that create power grasping affordances is of great value, as it can substantially increase the grasp success rates in such complex environments.

Precision grasp planning approaches [1] require the full knowledge of the object properties, such as shape, material, mass and pose to plan a successful grasp. This reliance on object specific modelling makes the grasp planning infeasible for real world scenarios due to perception errors and sensors uncertainty. As a result, power grasps [2]–[4] are preferred to compensate for perception errors. However, these approaches

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Fig. 1. Different ways that a push-grasping primitive can create free space around an object in order to establish a stable power grasp in clutter. A proper push-grasping can roll-in an object within the palm of the hand and roll out or translate other objects away from the hand’s closing region.

require free space around the object and thus are not applicable for highly cluttered scenes. Dealing with clutter means that the robot should rearrange the objects in order to create enough space for the robot fingers to wrap around an object and perform a stable power grasp. Inspired by [5], we employ pushing actions to roll an object into the robot hand and roll out or translate other objects away from the hand’s closing region (Fig. 1), creating the aforementioned free space, before closing the fingers. As shown in Fig. 2, the policy should properly select the pose of the hand, as well as the configuration of the fingers in order to establish a stable power grasp.

In this paper we propose a multi-fingered grasping policy that employs push-grasping actions to perform stable power grasps in cluttered scenes. In summary, this paper introduces the following contributions:

- A novel learned grasping policy that achieves robust power grasps in clutter scenes without assuming a segmentation of the scene.
- An efficient learning scheme that decouples the selection of hand pose and the selection of the hand’s finger configuration.
- Experimental evaluation that demonstrates superior per-

Fig. 2. Illustration of different push-grasps for the same cluttered scene. Blue color denotes the object finally grasped. (a) Selected initial pose results to an unstable precision grasp, (b) Selected initial pose and finger configuration results to unstable power grasp of two objects, (c) The selected initial hand pose and finger configuration results to roll an object into the hand, the creation of free space with surrounding obstacles and finally stable power grasp.

formance of the proposed grasping policy over baselines and generalization to unseen objects.

In the following section the related work is presented. Section III describes the problem, the assumptions and the state representation, followed by Section IV that describes the push-grasping policy that is proposed. In Section V experimental evaluation is presented and finally conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Robotic grasping has evolved a lot over the last two decades. Bohg et al. [6] divide the various methods of robotic grasping to analytic and data-driven. Analytic methods assume full knowledge of the object’s geometry and physics to calculate stable grasps [7], but tend to not transfer well to the real world due to the inability to model physical parameters related to the interaction between a manipulator and an object [8], [9]. For this reason data-driven approaches have risen in popularity in recent years. Instead of relying exclusively on analytic understanding of the physics and geometry of the object, data driven methods learn to predict grasps based on a large dataset of successful grasps. The datasets are generated either manually or by exhaustively performing simulated grasps on 3D scenes [10]–[12] and keeping the successful ones. Grasp simulators are used to process 3D meshes of objects and compute the stability of a grasp based upon the grasp wrench space. However, this limits the approach to the range of objects previously seen. Recent works deal with unknown objects either by performing shape completion and then plan grasps on the completed shapes [13], [14] or by detecting object grasp poses directly from images [15]–[18]. Although these methods can generalize across different objects, they

consider the robotic grasping of a single isolated object in an uncluttered environment.

Most of the existing approaches that assume cluttered environments are restricted to parallel grippers and hence to precision grasping. Gumatieri *et al.* [19] proposed a grasp pose detection method that randomly samples a number of antipodal grasps from a 3-D point cloud and then assigns quality scores to each grasp through a convolution neural network. Mousavian *et al.* [20] alleviate the need of random sampling by training a variational autoencoder to sample a set of grasps. Both approaches produce stable grasps, but under the assumption of antipodal contacts. Recent approaches utilize multi-fingered hands to perform precision grasping in clutter [21], [22]. However, planning precision grasps in dense clutter increases the uncertainty of stable grasping. On the contrary, Kiatos *et al.* [3] plan power grasps given the point cloud of the scene and the geometry of the robot hand. Although, they demonstrated high grasp success rates, their approach require sampling collision-free grasps, which either have low quality or are non-existent in a dense cluttered environment.

To enable high-quality power grasps in dense clutter, pre-grasp actions should be performed. Zeng *et al.* [23] employed pushing actions in order to increase grasping affordances in high clutter but they considered only top-down precision grasps for flat objects. Tang *et al.* [24] expanded the grasping action space by learning 6-DoF grasping policies. Although, they demonstrated increased grasp success rate in a wider set of objects, they only consider precision grasps.

Similar to the problem addressed in this work is [5], which uses pushing as a preceding realignment step for stable power grasping. In contrast to our data-driven approach, their approach requires the full knowledge of the object properties and pose in order to perform a successful power grasp.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider the problem of planning stable power grasps of objects in dense clutter that are supported by a surface by employing a single push-grasping action. We learn a function that takes as input a visual observation I and outputs the best push-grasping action, i.e. the action that would lead to the most stable power grasp of any object in the scene. Since we do not specify any target object, we do not need any segmentation of the scene.

A. Assumptions

We assume that there is a planar squared surface on which random objects with arbitrary geometry are resting in a tightly packed configuration. The inertia frame is placed on the center of the surface as shown in Fig. 3(a), with its z -axis, normal to the surface and opposite to the gravity vector. We assume that the space above the surface is included in the workspace of the robot allowing the robot hand to reach any desired pose. We also assume that the hand can reach opposable finger configurations like the ones depicted in Fig. 3(b).

Fig. 3. Visualization of the support surface, the objects, the robotic hand, the inertia frame and parameters of the push-grasp primitive. (a) Illustration of the environment including the support surface, the objects and the camera. The inertia frame T_w is placed at the center of the table. The visual input I is a map that represents an orthographic top-down view based on the camera pose T_c . (b) Parametrization of the push-grasping primitive.

B. Motion Primitive

The push-grasping primitive is a straight motion of the robot palm along a line segment $[p_1, p_2] \in \mathbb{R}^3$ placed above and in parallel to the support surface (Fig. 3), followed by closing the fingers. Notice that the palm’s normal vector is always aligned with the direction of the line segment. We parameterise the push-grasping primitive as $a = \{p, \theta, \alpha, d\}$ by:

- the initial position $p \in \mathbb{R}^2$ that the push starts. The distance z from the table is kept fixed during the primitive execution. Note that $p_1 = [p, z]$.
- The angle θ of the vector normal to the hand’s palm with respect to the x axis of the inertia frame, which defines the pushing direction. Note that in our case θ receives discrete values.
- The aperture α of the hand during the push, which is the distance of the fingers in an opposable finger configuration (Fig. 3(b)) and is kept fixed during the execution of the primitive’s pushing part.
- The pushing distance d of the hand.

The final point p_2 is determined by the angle θ and the pushing distance d , i.e. $p_2 = p_1 + d[\cos(\theta), \sin(\theta), 0]^T$. Note that the pushing distance d and the height z are not learnable parameters and are empirically set to $d = 0.15$ m and $z = 0.1$ m. In particular, the height z is determined as the minimum distance from the table that the robot hand can move freely without collision with the support surface during the execution of the motion primitive.

C. State Representation

We represent the visual input I as a depth heightmap of the scene. To compute this heightmap, we fuse depth images captured with calibrated cameras using known intrinsics and extrinsics. Specifically, each captured image is projected onto a 3-D point cloud and orthographically back-projected upward in the gravity direction to construct a heightmap image as shown in Fig. 3(a). Note that the depth heightmap is normalized, i.e. mean subtracted and divided by the standard deviation. This scalar height-from-bottom information enables

the deep models to learn features that are rich in geometric shape.

The edges of the heightmap are defined with respect to the workspace limits. In our experiments, this area covers 0.5×0.5 m tabletop surface. The heightmaps have image resolution 100×100 and hence each pixel $i \in I$ represents a 5×5 mm vertical column of 3-D space in the robot’s workspace.

IV. LEARNING A PUSH-GRASPING POLICY

Our system consists of two modules: a fully-convolutional neural network (FCN) which predicts the optimal pose of the hand, i.e. the initial position p and the angle θ , and a convolutional neural network (CNN) which predicts the aperture α of the hand. Decoupling the action space offers efficient learning, since each network focuses on learning a different part of the action.

A. Pose-FCN module

The FCN network is a seven-layer fully convolutional residual network similar to the one of [26], with its architecture shown in Fig. 4. This network takes as input the depth heightmap I and outputs a probability map Q with the same size and resolution as that of the input image I . Each value of a pixel $q_i \in Q$ represents the probability of a successful power grasp when executing a push-grasping action that starts from the p corresponding to the pixel $i \in I$, given that the aperture is unknown. To simplify learning of the angle θ , we account for different pushing directions by rotating the input heightmap into $k = 16$ discrete orientations (different multiplies of 22.5°) and then consider only horizontal pushes to the right. Rotations are done with nearest-neighbor sampling to avoid blurring artifacts, as well as 0-padding to maintain fixed image sizes. Thus, during training each heightmap is rotated according to the angle θ before feeding to the FCN. On the contrary, during inference the input to the FCN is $k = 16$ rotated heightmaps. The pixel with the highest probability amongst all 16 output maps determines the parameters (p^*, θ^*) for the push-grasping primitive.

This visual state and action representation has been shown to provide sample efficiency when it is combined with fully-convolutional networks [23], [26]. Each pixel prediction shares convolutional features for all push-grasping locations and orientations (i.e. translation and rotation equivariance). In [23], [26] it is proved that spatial equivariance increase learning efficiency for vision-based manipulation tasks. To this end, FCN excel in modeling complex distributions anchored on visual features.

B. Aperture-CNN module

The CNN network of this module takes as input a pre-processed heightmap I_α of the scene and regresses to the optimal aperture α of the hand. Specifically, the depth heightmap I is first rotated according to optimal angle θ^* and then cropped with respect to optimal initial position p^* to form a 64×64 map. The optimal p^* and θ^* are produced by the Pose-FCN module. This representation has two benefits. First, the rotation

Fig. 4. Illustration of the proposed push-grasping policy. The Pose-FCN is a ResNet-7, where $\text{Conv}(k, c)$ denotes a convolutional layer with $k \times k$ filters and c channels, $\text{RB}(c)$ denotes a residual block [25] with two convolutional layers using 3×3 filters and c channels, MP denotes a 3×3 max pooling layer with stride=2, UP denotes a bilinear $2 \times$ upsampling layer and $\text{FC}(n)$ denotes a fully connected layer with n neurons.

of the depth heightmap I reduces the variability of the visual representation and secondly the crop operation enables the network to focus its attention around the area that the push-grasping action starts, thus discarding irrelevant information. We convert the input image to a 3-channel tensor $(I_\alpha, I_\alpha, I_\alpha)$ and we fed it into a ResNet-50 [25] pretrained on ImageNet [27] for feature extraction, followed by two fully connected layers interleaved with ReLU activation functions. The final layer is a fully connected layer followed by a sigmoid function to predict the aperture.

C. Learning from Demonstrations

We assume access to a dataset of n demonstrations $D = \{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_n\}$ acquired by running a random exploration policy and keeping only the successful grasps. Each demonstration $\zeta_i = (I_i, a_i)$ is a pair of a depth heightmap I_i and a push-grasping action a_i .

1) *Successful grasp definition*: For keeping the samples that result to successful grasps we assume that there is a criterion that evaluates the state of the system and decides whether the grasp is successful. We define a grasp as successful if the following conditions are true:

- Only one object has been grasped, as grasping more than one objects could lead to grasp instability.
- The grasp is a power grasp, i.e. the contact area is not limited to the hand's fingertips, but extends to other links of the fingers and the palm.
- The grasp is stable, i.e. if the object is lifted, it will remain within the hand.

In our case, another condition is added making the successful grasp definition stricter:

- the grasp is successful if empty space was created around the grasped object during the pushing part of the push-grasping primitive, i.e. its distance from the rest of the objects was increased.

We call this the *singulation condition* and as it will be seen in Section V, training on a dataset collected also with this fourth condition, results to increased grasping performance for heavily cluttered environments with respect to training on a dataset collected with only the first three.

2) *Dataset generation*: To generate this dataset we guide the exploration to select actions a_i that start close to an object with direction pointing towards it, in order to increase the chances of successful grasps. Hence, for exploring initial positions p , we randomly sample a point from the set of heightmap pixels $i \in I$ whose minimum distance from any object is 0.1 – 0.15 m. For each sampled p , we compute the angle θ by the line that starts from p and ends in an object contour point randomly chosen, which ensures that the push direction always points towards an object. Finally, the aperture α is sampled from a uniform distribution between the aperture limits.

3) *Training*: We train both networks in a supervised manner. During training the FCN network, we randomly sample batches of heightmap-action pairs, that can be unpacked into the binary one-hot pixel map $Y_{pose} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times k}$ for training the FCN network and $y_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ for training the regression network. The loss for training the FCN network is the cross-entropy loss between the one-hot pixel maps and the output probabilities Q , i.e. $L = -\mathbb{E}_{Y_{pose}} [\log Q]$. While we only have labels for a single pixel per dense probability map, gradients are passed to all other pixels via image-wide softmax. For the CNN network that predicts the aperture α , we use Huber loss. Both networks are trained using the Adam optimizer with learning rate 10^{-4} . The batch size for Pose-FCN is 1 and for the Aperture-CNN is 4.

V. RESULTS

We conducted experiments both in simulation and in a real environment to evaluate the performance of the proposed push-grasping policy. The goals of the experiments are twofold: 1)

Fig. 5. The CAD models of the two object sets used during training (seen) and during testing (seen and unseen). These object sets were created by the YCB object set [29] and from KIT object set [30].

to investigate if the performance of the proposed push-grasping policy is superior over baseline policies and 2) to demonstrate the robust transfer in a real world robotic system without a significant drop in performance.

A. Simulation experiments

The simulation environment consists of a floating Barrett hand and a 0.5×0.5 m tabletop workspace with 2 simulated 640×480 RGB-D cameras pointing towards the workspace: one stationed in front of the workspace and one in a top view. Our method does not require 2 cameras but having more cameras improves visual coverage. For example, in our real experiments we use only one camera.

Each grasp is executed by the push-grasping primitive, as described in Section III-B. After closing the fingers, the hand is raised upwards by 20 cm. We counted a grasp to be successful by checking the conditions described in Section IV-C1. In particular, we check (a) if only one object is positioned in 20cm above the surface, (b) if there are contact points between the object’s mesh and the mesh of the palm and/or the finger proximal links, (c) the object was fully lifted and pertained to the hand for 5 seconds. We use the Bullet physics engine [28] to advance the simulation. All the dynamic parameters of the simulated environment are kept to their default values.

1) *Policies*: To address the aforementioned goals, we compare the performance of the following learned approaches:

- **Grasping-only** is a grasping policy that uses the same pixel-wise state and action space formulation as our proposed method without the pushing part of the primitive action. Thus, the method learns a grasping pose $a = \{p, \theta\}$ that achieves power grasping while the non-learned pushing distance parameter d is set to 0 instead of the fixed value 0.15m. The height z is kept fixed to 0.1m. We collect a dataset of successful power grasps that met the first three conditions as described in Section IV-C1 without including the singulation condition, since the robot hand cannot create any extra free space around the grasped object without the pushing part. Note that a grasp is determined as successful if the robot hand

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION ON SEEN AND UNSEEN OBJECTS (%)

Metric: Object Set:	SR-1		SR-N		SC	
	Seen	Unseen	Seen	Unseen	Seen	Unseen
Grasping-only	55.0	28.0	27.4	14.4	60.0	38.9
PPG	71.0	63.0	70.3	69.7	70.4	68.3
sPPG	79.0	83.0	87.8	87.4	84.1	83.9
fixed-sPPG	70.0	75.0	81.8	86.3	82.2	83.8
heur-PPG	34.0	28.0	42.6	37.5	44.6	36.2

TABLE II
PERCENTAGE OF SUCCESSFUL GRASPS THAT SATISFY THE SINGULATION CONDITION (%)

Metric: Object Set:	SR-1		SR-N		SC	
	Seen	Unseen	Seen	Unseen	Seen	Unseen
PPG	35.0	23.0	30.5	18.5	40.8	31.3
sPPG	68.0	63.0	69.6	64.5	70.7	67.0
fixed-sPPG	52.0	60.0	63.3	60.9	67.4	63.3

reaches the grasping pose without collisions. We train only the Pose-FCN module to predict the grasping pose and keep the aperture α fixed to the mean aperture value, i.e. the average between the aperture limits. Note that the mean aperture is wide enough so as the robot hand can grasp any of the objects.

- **Power Push-Grasping (PPG)** is a push-grasping policy that is trained with a dataset that contains demonstrations that met just the first three conditions of a successful grasp of Section IV-C1. Note that even though we do not enforce the singulation condition to be satisfied, some demonstrations may singulate the object before grasping it.
- **Power Push-Grasping with singulation (sPPG)** is the proposed push-grasping policy which is trained with demonstrations that met all four conditions, including the singulation condition.
- **Fixed Aperture Power Push-Grasping with singulation (fixed-sPPG)** is a push-grasping policy that predicts only the optimal pose of the hand, while the aperture is kept fixed with a value that corresponds to the mean aperture. Note that every object can be rolled into the robot hand with the mean aperture value. Finally, this policy is trained with demonstrations that met all four conditions described in Section IV-C1.

All datasets contain $n = 15$ K demonstrations, collected by sampling objects from the “Seen” object set (illustrated in Fig. 5). The aperture limits are set empirically based on the object size variety between $[0.09, 0.2]^T$ m. Finally, to avoid overfitting we train all policies with early stopping.

In addition to these learned policies we design a heuristic policy as a baseline that uses the power push-grasping primitive (**heur-PPG**), in order to check if a simple heuristic rule can make valuable decisions for the task. For making heuristic decisions, we first perform clustering on the heightmap applying the DBSCAN algorithm [31] on the state representation I and we select the smallest cluster. The intuition behind the

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION ON CHALLENGING SCENES (%)

Metric Object	SR-1							SR-N							SC						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	Avg	1	2	3	4	5	6	Avg	1	2	3	4	5	6	Avg
PPG	66.6	100	16.6	100	50.0	16.6	58.3	85.0	78.9	61.9	96.2	56.2	23.0	68.6	82.7	76.1	51.6	97.2	45.2	11.1	60.6
sPPG	100	100	83.3	83.3	83.3	83.3	88.6	94.4	90	90	95	95	72.2	89.4	86.6	90.2	90.2	80.5	93	71.1	85.2

selection of the smallest cluster is that it probably contains a single object and thus the grasp will be more stable. Similarly to the random policy used for dataset generation, we randomly sample a pixel around the smallest cluster whose minimum distance from the cluster is between $0.1 - 0.15$ m, which denotes the initial point p . The angle θ is computed from the line that starts from point p and ends in the cluster’s centroid. Then, we check if p results in a collision-free placement of the hand. If this is not the case, two new p , θ are sampled until a collision-free p is found. The push distance is defined as the distance between the initial point p and cluster’s centroid. Finally, the aperture α is selected so as to fit the cluster’s largest dimension.

2) *Evaluation Metrics*: To evaluate the policies we run N episodes. The scene at the start of the episode is initialized by placing the objects in a packed configuration and a grasp is attempted in each step. Each episode terminates when a single object is lying on the table or no power push-grasp actions can change the scene. The latter can happen if there are only flat objects on the scene or if the robot threw the objects off the table during the primitive execution. Note that we do not consider grasping a single object due to its simplicity. A grasp is determined as successful if the three conditions of Section III-E1 are satisfied. Notice that the singulation condition is not necessary for stable grasping and thus it is not used during evaluation.

Our evaluation metrics are: (a) the grasp success rate (SR-1) that takes into account only the first attempted grasp of each episode (b) the grasp success rate that takes into account every attempted grasp (SR-N) and (c) the average scene clearance rate (SC) defined as the number of successful grasps divided by the number of the objects on the table at the start of the episode, averaged across the N episodes. During an episode the push-grasping actions can reduce the levels of the initial clutter by pushing and removing objects and hence the SR-1 indicates the performance of the policies in heavily dense clutter, while SR-N includes also grasps that are attempted to less cluttered scenes.

3) *Random arrangements*: We evaluate the performance of the aforementioned baselines on scenes with randomly packed configurations. First, we perform $N = 100$ evaluation episodes with objects sampled only from the "Seen" object set, shown in Fig. 5 and then we perform another $N = 100$ episodes sampling objects only from the "Unseen" object set. These object sets were created by the YCB object set [29] and the KIT object set [30].

As shown in Table I, the **Grasping-only** policy performs poorly due to the lack of collision free grasp affordances.

Fig. 6. Sample of challenging scenes for the 6 objects. Note that we create 7 scenes for each object. Each scene contains 2 to 7 instances of the same object in a tightly packed configuration. A sample scene with 2 instances is not illustrated due to its simplicity.

The superiority of all learned push-grasping policies indicates the need of the pushing part of the push-grasping primitive in highly cluttered environments, since it can create free space around the object allowing the fingers to wrap around it and resulting to a stable power grasp. Furthermore, as the results indicate, the proposed policy **sPPG** supersedes the performance of the **PPG** policy. This demonstrates that training the agent with a dataset acquired with demonstrations that incorporate the singulation condition, leads to a more effective and robust grasping policy since it increases the grasp success rate. This does not mean that successful grasps always singulate the object before grasping as demonstrated by the results in Table II; e.g the **sPPG** achieves 79% successful grasps in "Seen" objects (Table I) whereas 68% are the successful grasps that singulate the object (Table II). Moreover, the difference in performance of **fixed-sPPG** and **sPPG** demonstrates that learning the aperture is vital to predict a successful push-grasping action. Finally, the heuristic policy **heur-PPG** presents poor performance, demonstrating that the task cannot be easily solved by simple heuristics given only raw visual information. The most common failures are due to the unreliable object detection with the DBSCAN clustering.

The SR-1 of the **sPPG** policy demonstrates that the proposed policy can achieve stable power grasping in dense clutter, while the high SR-N indicates that the **sPPG** overall produces stable power grasps regardless the amount of scene clutter. The high SC value indicates that the proposed **sPPG** policy implicitly learns the order of grasping the objects, which results to clutter reduction of the scene and achieves scene clearance. Finally, the policy also seems to have similar

performance between seen and unseen objects, indicating that generalizes well to novel objects.

4) *Challenging arrangements*: To test the performance of the proposed policy on challenging cases with adversarial clutter, we create scenes that contain multiple instances of the same object in a tightly packed configuration (Fig. 6). We use 6 objects shown in Fig. 6 in sample scenes. They belong to both "Seen" and "Unseen" object sets. For each object we create 7 scenes that include 2 to 7 object instances and we run each episode until completion. The results are shown in Table III with object id referring to the objects of Fig. 6 enumerated from left to right. As it can be seen by the results the **sPPG** policy presents a very good performance, given that it never saw this type of challenging scenes during training. Note that **PPG** fails to grasp thin objects (e.g scenes in the last column of Fig. 6), due to the fact that it grasps two objects simultaneously. This demonstrate the importance of creating space around the grasped object before closing the fingers.

B. Real Experiments

Our real world setup consists of a UR5e robotic arm and the BarrettHand BH8-282 as the robotic hand. For perception data, RGB-D images are captured from an Intel RealSense D455 camera, statically mounted on a fixed tripod overlooking the tabletop setting. We performed 25 experiments with an object set which consists of 7 objects similar to the ones used in simulation experiments as shown in Fig. 7. The objects are placed in random tightly packed configurations.

The conducted experiments consist of the following steps. At first, the depth heightmap I is generated using an acquired depth image and then is fed to the Pose-FCN and subsequently to Aperture-CNN to predict the initial pose and aperture for the push-grasping primitive. If the predicted action is out of the robot's workspace, the next best action was chosen. Specifically, we only keep the actions that correspond to orientations that are reachable by the robot, and thus we do not take into consideration the last seven rotated heightmaps.

For every scene, we initialized the robot to the joint configuration $[-0.0027, -1.6227, -2.5143, -2.1462, -1.5735, -0.7854]^T$ as shown in Fig. 7. To execute a grasp, we plan smooth trajectories in the Cartesian space in order to move the robot arm to the initial pose defined by the parameters p_1 and θ and the fingers were shaped symmetrically according to the predicted aperture α . Then, the pushing action was executed, followed by closing the fingers to their final configuration. Subsequently constant torques were applied to the finger joints for 5 seconds. Finally, the robot hand was raised upwards by 30 cm. We consider a grasp to be successful if a single object was fully lifted and pertained to the hand. We show several video recordings of these test runs on our paper webpage¹.

The **sPPG** policy achieves 76 % in SR-1, 82.5 % in SR-N and 78.73 % in SC in the real environment. These results demonstrate that the proposed policy is robustly transferred to a real world scenario. In particular, high SR-1 indicates that the **sPPG** can produce power grasps in dense clutter,

Fig. 7. Experimental setup for real world experiments.

while high SR-N demonstrates the overall robustness of the proposed policy. Furthermore, the proposed policy achieves scene clearance in the real environment as shown from the high SC value due to the fact that push-grasping actions lead to objects rearrangement which reduces the initial clutter and thus generates more stable grasps. Although the results indicate that the learned policy is robustly transferred to a real world scenario, a small drop in success rate compared to simulation is observed. This difference is accounted to the fact that the best action is not always executed due to the limitations of the hardware and due to the discrepancy in the physics between simulation and real environment.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we addressed the problem of grasping in highly cluttered scenes. To achieve that, we proposed a push-grasping policy that rolls an object into the robot hand or roll out other objects from the robot hand's closing region. This creates space for the fingers to wrap around an object and perform a stable power grasp. Results demonstrate that the proposed approach can generate stable grasps in challenging scenes with dense clutter outperforming baselines and that the learned policy can be robustly transferred to a real world environment.

However, its limitations suggest directions for future work. First, the height z from the table that the push starts, limits the number of objects that can be grasped, since shorter objects cannot be manipulated. This limitation comes from the fact that the robot hand should not collide with the table during the parallel motion. Thus, generating 6-DoF push-grasping actions is an interesting approach that will not be limited to parallel table pushing actions. Secondly, the proposed policy uses only a single primitive i.e. push-grasping. It would be interesting to investigate how different grasping policies that exploit contact with the environment [32], can be used in conjunction with the proposed push-grasping policy in order to grasp a wider set of objects. Finally, it would also be interesting to investigate the performance of a push-grasping policy for the unpacking operation.

¹<https://robot-clutter.github.io/ppg>

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